

Kinetics of Oxidation of Acetyl Acetone by Selenium Dioxide

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The kinetics of oxidation of acetyl acetone in 50% (v/v) acetic acid-water by selenium dioxide has been studied. The reaction follows first order kinetics with respect to both selenium dioxide and acetyl acetone. The effects of sulphuric acid, neutral salts, solvent polarity and temperature on the rate of oxidation have been studied. The energy of activation, frequency factor, entropy of activation and free energy of activation have values 15.56 ± 0.6 kcal mol⁻¹, $4.29 \pm 0.3 \times 10^6$ dm³ mol⁻¹sec⁻¹, -27.9 ± 1.0 e.u. and 24.96 ± 0.8 kcal mol⁻¹, respectively. A mechanism of oxidation, consistent with experimental observations has been proposed.

SELENIUM dioxide has been extensively used as an oxidant in many organic reactions¹. It has also been used in the kinetics of oxidation of some organic compounds²⁻⁵. However, no attempt has been made so far to study the kinetics of oxidation of acetyl acetone by selenium dioxide which we report in this communication.

Experimental

Acetyl acetone (B.D.H.), selenium dioxide (Loba) and acetic acid (B.D.H.) and other chemicals of A.R. quality were used. The stock solution of selenium dioxide was prepared in distilled water and was standardised iodometrically.

The reactions were studied in a thermostat ($\pm 0.1^\circ$). The velocity of the reaction was determined by estimating the unreacted selenium dioxide by iodometric method⁶. The order of reaction with respect to selenium dioxide was determined by isolation method, whereas that with respect to acetyl acetone was determined by Vant Hoff's differential method.

Stoichiometry and products: The stoichiometry of the reaction was determined by allowing the reaction mixture containing excess of selenium dioxide (10 times) over acetyl acetone at 50° until there was no change in selenium dioxide concentration. It was observed that one mole of acetyl acetone requires one mole of selenium dioxide for complete oxidation. The stoichiometric equation can, therefore, be written as

The product 2,3,4-pentanetrione was identified by preparing its 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone. The other product selenium was tested by its characteristic spot test⁶.

Results and Discussion

Dependence of reaction on reactants: The variation in selenium dioxide concentration (Table 1) showed that the order in selenium dioxide is one. The pseudo first order rate constants were calculated from the integrated first order equation. The rate constants were calculated with an accuracy of $\pm 3\%$ in duplicate kinetic runs.

[SeO ₂] × 10 ³ M	2.5	5.0	7.5	10.0
	12.5	20.0	30.0	35.0
10 ³ k min ⁻¹ (k = k ₁ /2.303)	2.92	1.94	1.82	1.62
	1.44	1.26	1.03	0.91

The variation in acetyl acetone concentration (Table 2) showed that pseudo first order rate constants in selenium dioxide were directly proportional to acetyl acetone concentrations. The constancy of k₂ values (second order rate constants) shown in last column of Table 2 clearly indicates that the reaction follows first order kinetics in acetyl acetone.

[Acetyl acetone] M	0.50	0.75	1.00	1.25	1.50
10 ³ k min ⁻¹ (k = k ₁ /2.303)	1.62	2.61	3.71	4.87	5.88
10 ² k ₂ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ min ⁻¹	0.32	0.35	0.37	0.39	0.39
(k ₂ = k/[Acetyl acetone])					

Effect of sulphuric acid, neutral salts, acetic acid and temperature: The presence of sulphuric acid accelerates the rate of oxidation. The rate is further accelerated with increase in the concentration

TABLE 3

Temp. = 50°; [Acetyl acetone] = 0.50 M; Solvent: HOAc-H₂O = 50% (v/v); [SeO₂] = 0.01 M

	k ^a	1.62	1.85	1.95	2.14	2.65	3.28
		4.34	5.5	6.92	8.15	14.20	19.94
	k ^b	1.62	1.61	1.61	1.6	1.57	
	k ^c	1.62	1.60	1.60	1.57	1.55	
	k ^d	1.77	1.69	1.62	1.5	1.35	
	k ^e	1.62	2.43	3.38	4.97	6.95	
Effect of H ₂ SO ₄	k ^a	0.000	0.010	0.025	0.050	0.10	0.25
		0.50	1.0	1.5	2.0	2.5	3.0 M
Effect of KCl	k ^b	0.000	0.004	0.006	0.008	0.010 M	
Effect of Na ₂ SO ₄	k ^c	0.000	0.002	0.004	0.006	0.008 M	
Effect of %HOAc	k ^d	30	40	50	60	70	
Effect of temp., °C	k ^e	50	55	60	65	70	

Values of rate constants, k = 10³k₁/2.303 min⁻¹.

of sulphuric acid. The data show that the dependence of rate of oxidation on sulphuric acid concentration is not simple (Table 3).

The added neutral salts such as KCl, Na₂SO₄ have nearly no influence on the rate of reaction in dilute solution (Table 3). The fact that the primary salt effect on the rate of reactions being negligible suggests that at least one of the reacting species in the rate determining step is a neutral molecule⁷.

The study of the effect of solvent polarity (varying acetic acid-water mixture) on the rate of oxidation shows very small dependence on the solvent composition. Increase in percentage of water increases the rate (Table 3). The plot of log k vs D - 1/2D + 1 was linear, suggesting that the reaction between acetyl acetone and selenium dioxide is a dipole-dipole reaction⁸.

The kinetics of oxidation of acetyl acetone was studied at different temperatures (Table 3). The plot of log k vs 1/T was linear. The various activation parameters were evaluated, using Arrhenius and Eyring equations with a linear least squares method. The calculated values of energy of activation (E_a), frequency factor (A), entropy of activation (ΔS[‡]) and free energy of activation (ΔG[‡]) are 15.56 ± 0.6 kcal mol⁻¹, 4.29 ± 0.3 × 10⁶ dm³ mol⁻¹ sec⁻¹, -27.9 ± 1.0 e.u. and 24.96 ± 0.8 kcal mol⁻¹, respectively.

The rates of enolisation of ketones are usually measured by reactions such as halogenation⁹, racemisation¹⁰, and deuteration¹¹. All these reactions are of zero order. Hence if the rate of enolisation of acetyl acetone is to be regarded rate determining, then the rate of reaction would not depend on the selenium dioxide concentration contrary to the observation. Hence, the rate determining enolisation is ruled out. Such slow stage in the oxidation of desoxybenzoin by selenium dioxide has already been ruled out³.

In aqueous medium selenium dioxide is present mainly as selenious acid (eqn. 1), which in the absence of a strong acid is partially dissociated into biselenite ion and H⁺ ion (eqn. 2).

It was reported^{3,4,12} that selenium dioxide may exist in aqueous acetic acid mixture, in the absence of a strong mineral acid, as HSeO₃⁺, H₂SeO₃ and AcHSeO₃, while in the presence of a strong mineral acid as HSeO₃⁺, H₂SeO₃⁺ and AcH₂SeO₃⁺. Although HSeO₃⁺, being a stronger electrophile compared to H₂SeO₃⁺, may not be present in sufficiently high concentration in aqueous solution³, therefore, the mechanism of oxidation is to be considered in terms of oxidising species H₂SeO₃ or AcHSeO₃ in the absence of a strong mineral acid and H₂SeO₃⁺ or AcH₂SeO₃⁺ in the presence of a strong mineral acid.

The rate constant for oxidation of acetyl acetone (I) increases with decrease in concentration of selenium dioxide. Since selenious acid dissociates more in dilute solution, it may be presumed that biselenite ion is the effective oxidising species. But it has been found that the complete inhibition of oxidation of acetyl acetone occurs in aqueous solution when a sufficient quantity of acetate was added to ensure half neutralisation of selenious acid^{13,14}.

Hence biselenite ion as an effective oxidant in the present case is ruled out. It has also been reported⁴ that biselenite ion is not an effective oxidant in the oxidation of ketones by selenium dioxide.

It is known¹⁵⁻¹⁷ that selenium(IV) dimerises in aqueous acidic media. In the concentration range 0.003-0.009 M, the extent of monomer varies from 97-92%. At high concentration range 0.01-0.1 M, the percent monomeric form varies from 92-62% and still at high concentration range 0.2-0.5 M the percent monomer ranges 50-36%. In the present investigation the concentration range of selenium(IV) employed is 0.0025 to 0.030 M, therefore, selenium(IV) will exist both in monomeric and dimeric forms in the reaction mixture. The pseudo first order rate constants in selenium dioxide are found to increase with the decrease in selenium dioxide concentration in the presence of 0.60 M HClO₄ at μ = 1.0 M (NaCl) as well as in aqueous acetic acid in the absence of HClO₄ (Table 4). This probably suggests that selenious acid also exists both in monomeric and dimeric forms in aqueous acetic

acid medium. Thus the increase in the rate constant of oxidation with the decreasing concentration of selenium dioxide may be attributed to lower concentration of dimeric selenium(IV), that is, by assuming that as an oxidant the dimer is less reactive than the monomer, similar to cerium(IV)¹⁸.

TABLE 4

Temp. = 50°; [Acetyl acetone] = 0.5 M;
Solvent: HOAc-H₂O = 50% (v/v)

[SeO ₂] M	0.0025	0.005	0.010	0.020	0.030
t ₁₀ *k min ⁻¹	1.51	1.23	1.07	0.97	0.89
g ₁₀ *k min ⁻¹	2.32	1.94	1.62	1.26	1.03

t_k [HClO₄] = 0.60 M, μ = 1.0 M adjusted with NaCl.
g_k [HClO₄] = 0.00 M, μ = 0.0 M (k = k₁/2.303).

Mechanism: On the basis of experimental facts, the proposed mechanism involves attack of an electrophile, H₂SeO₃, on acetyl acetone (I) in a slow step to give an enol selenium(IV) ester (II). The latter rearranges in a series of fast steps to enol selenium(II) ester (III) and finally to 2,3,4-pentane-trione (IV).

References

1. N. RABJOHN in "Organic Reactions", ed. R. ADAMS, John Wiley, London, 1957, Vol. 5, p. 331.
2. F. R. DUKE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 419.
3. E. J. COREY and J. P. SCHAEFFER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **82**, 918.
4. J. P. SCHAEFFER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, **84** 713, 717.
5. K. J. SINGH and S. N. ANAND, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 363.
6. F. FRIGL, "Spot Tests", Elsevier, London, 1954, Vol. 1, p. 341.
7. BRONSTED, *Z. Physik. Chem.*, 1922, **102**, 169.
8. E. S. AMIS, *J. Chem. Educat.*, 1953, **30**, 351.
9. P. D. BARTLETT and C. H. STAUFFER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **75**, 2580.
10. S. K. SHU, C. K. INGOLD and C. L. WILSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 78.
11. K. F. BONHOEFFER and O. REITZ, *Phys. Chem. A*, 1937, 179.
12. J. P. SCHAEFFER, B. HORVATH and H. P. KLEIN, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1968, **33**, 2647.
13. H. HAGISAWA, *Bull. Inst. Phys. Chem. Res., Jpn.*, 1939, **18**, 648 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1940, **34**, 4965).
14. J. R. J. DIPPY, *Chem. Rev.*, 1939, **25**, 151.
15. F. J. HUGHES and D. S. MARTIN, JR., *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1955, **59**, 410.
16. L. BERCEA and L. G. SILLEN, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1971, **25**, 1260.
17. J. N. COOPER, M. WOODS, J. C. SULLIVAN and E. DEUTSCH, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1976, **15**, 2862.
18. B. D. BLANSEN and J. W. GRYSER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **79**, 540.